

Assessing Audit Committee Effectiveness on Real Earnings Management of Listed Non-Financial Firms in Nigeria

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Abstract

The study is aimed at investigating the potential impact of audit committee in the financial performance of listed non-financial firms in Nigeria for a period of 10 years spanning 2011-2021. The dependent variable of the study is real earnings management proxy Srivastava (2019) revised model while the independent variable of the study is audit committee proxy by audit committee independence, audit committee size, audit committee diversity and audit committee meetings. The study arrived at 760 firm year observations from a population of 113 listed non-financial companies in Nigeria; the extracted secondary data was analysed using PCSE and the results revealed that audit committee independence, audit committee size and audit committee meetings have no significant impact on real earnings management while only audit committee diversity among all the variables showed a significant positive impact on real earnings management of listed non-financial firms in Nigeria. The study recommends that the number of members in the audit committee should be increased by the relevant authority and the percentage of women in the composition in the audit committee should also be increased as this will help in reducing earnings management and improve the efficiency of the committee.

Keywords: Audit committee, Financial firms, Financial performance, Financial information, Real earnings management

Introduction

The main reason for the preparation and presentation of a reliable annual financial report in a timely manner by management of a company is to deliver mandatory annual financial information to major stakeholders. The financial Statement consists of qualitative and

quantitative information that stakeholders depend on to make informed decisions –""(Ghafran & OSullivan, 2017). Accounting earnings is a major element in the financial statement because it is been used by users in order to take informed decisions. However, managers take advantage of control they have over the accounting figures for personal benefits, covenants, raising capital and or to achieve corporate objectives of the company. This is because it is believed that reported earnings reflect underlying operating performance of the company and this action by management is commonly known as earnings management. The decided cases of financial scandals of World.com and Enron in the United States showed that earnings management is an opportunistic activity that chief executives engaged on. In recent years the most common form of earnings management (EM) occurs through real activities manipulation known as real earnings management (REM). Tabassam, Kaleem and Nazir (2014) argued that top management of companies manipulate the earnings of business organisations through real activities to reveal good results in the reporting accounting period, this is because since after the Sarbanes oxley Act (2002) issued strict rules which management perceived that manipulations through accruals are easily detected by the external auditor. The studies of many previous scholars posited that after the SOX Act (2002) implementation, the strict rules and regulations made many chief executives of companies to switch from manipulating earnings through accruals to real activities manipulations from the gained attention and recognition from organisations. It is contended that because REM is not subject to much controls and audits, media, covenant pressures, control by external scrutiny and representatives from politics. Therefore, managers prefer manipulating earnings by way of real activities rather than accrual EM. And again REM has a strange nature of disguise according to Roychowdhury (2006) noted several tactics that managers use to engage in REM, to reduce discretionary expenses, overproduce and or give discounts to boost sales in order to improve earnings reported for the current year.

Certainly, the presence of a well-structured audit committee (AC) has become mandatory for all publicly listed companies in the United Kingdom and the United States (as specified in the UK Corporate Governance Code, 2010, and the Sarbanes-Oxley Act, 2002). Corporate governance regulations emphasize the significant role of the audit committee. In Nigeria, the Securities and Exchange Commission (1999) issued a Code of Best Practices of Corporate Governance in 2011. The financial statement audit acts as a monitoring mechanism, assuring that the financial statements prepared by management are accurate and free from significant errors (Farouk & Hassan, 2014). The established AC is accountable for ensuring the preparation and presentation of the financial statements for auditing, as well as overseeing a smooth auditing process. The audit committee should be

formed with consideration for board diversity, encompassing various aspects such as age, race, ethnicity, gender, and social and cultural identities among employees within the organization. Ahmad et al. (2023) contended that an established audit committee with no bias in the composition will lead to a significantly reduced earnings management practices among entities. Moses, Ofurum and Egbe (2016) posits that a resourceful audit committee should enrich the quality of disclosure by performing duties such as giving approval of accounting principles and policies, giving remarks, evaluating and ensuring that the accounting and internal control mechanisms are effective. The aim of establishing the AC will be achieved if the committee ensures that the presented financial statement is free from material statements and that it depicts the true view of financial position and financial performance of the business organisation.

The study is aimed at investigating EM in companies through real activities manipulations and the idea is because the study is testing a revised model of Roychowdhury (2006) by Srivastava (2019) model and the model is suited most for companies that are engaged in production and sales of goods and services. This current study, if not the first then it is among the first studies to have been undertaken in Nigeria to examine the relationship between the dependent and independent variables of the study by adopting the model of Srivastava (2019).

Problem Statement

The trigger for this study is resulting from most of the recent reported accounting fraud cases around the world in 2021 such as Tal education group, Wirecard, Westpoint, Nikola, Wells Fargo, Tesla, Luckin coffee one of the biggest companies in China which is also listed in U.S stock exchange was found with scam in its operations where actual sales had a significant difference with reported sales, an accounting error that inflated the statement of financial position in-accurately with \$2.3b. Patisserie was also discovered to be potentially engaged in fraudulent accounting irregularities in 2018. The case of Cadbury Plc., Lever brothers Nigeria Plc. and Nestle if not the famous then are amongst the most prominent accounting manipulative cases in Nigeria, the recent reported accounting fraud cases of Oando, Unilever, Arik airlines showed that the earnings manipulations were done through real activities. To problematize in order have a grounded problem for this study, most of the aforementioned accounting fraud cases revealed that there is negligence and or compromise on the part of the audit committee who is saddled with the responsibility by the board of directors to ensure that fraud and errors are avoided in the process of preparing and reporting the mandatory annual financial statement. This is one of the reasons the study relied upon to examine the responsibility of the audit committee in

ensuring that manipulations through real earnings are mitigated to the barest minimum and this also serve as a motivation to dig in to investigate the subject matter of this study. For these reasons various studies have been undertaken in the field of accounting to investigate the impact of audit committee on earnings management but findings of most of the studies were mixed and inclusive paving gap for other researchers to explore this area and again most of the previous studies tend to investigate accounting manipulations through the accruals of earnings method but in this study the manipulations through real activities is prioritised thereby paving a methodological gap for this study to fill.

Objective of the Study

The main objective this study is to assess the impact of audit committee effectiveness on real earnings management of listed non-financial companies in Nigeria. The specific objectives of the study are:

- i. To examine the impact of audit committee independence on real earnings management of listed non-financial companies in Nigeria.
- ii. To investigate the impact of audit committee size on real earnings management of listed non-financial companies in Nigeria.
- iii. To assess the impact of audit committee diversity on real earnings management of listed non-financial companies in Nigeria.
- iv. To examine the impact of audit committee meetings on real earnings management of listed non-financial companies in Nigeria.

Hypotheses of the Study

In line with the objectives of the study, the following hypotheses are formulated in null form:

H_{01} Audit committee independence has no significant impact on real earnings management of listed non-financial companies in Nigeria.

H_{02} Audit committee size has no significant impact on real earnings management of listed non-financial companies in Nigeria.

H_{03} Audit committee diversity has no significant impact on real earnings management of listed non-financial companies in Nigeria.

H_{04} Audit committee meetings have no significant impact on real earnings management of listed non-financial companies in Nigeria.

Scope of the Study

This study examines the impact of AC on REM and is strictly restricted to committee on audit and listed non-financial companies on the Nigerian stock exchange floor (NSE). The study covers ten (10) years, from 20011-2020. The residuals of Srivastava (2019) model is

used as dependent variable proxy for real earnings management in this study while AC independence, AC meetings, size of the AC and financial expertise of the AC committee on audit serve as independent variable proxies for audit committee in the study.

Significance of the Study

The findings of the study are expected to contribute both practically and theoretically to practitioners and academicians. This research will contribute to existing literatures on the relationship between AC and REM. The research aims to contribute to the existing body of knowledge and also offer valuable quantitative data. The study intends to be relevant to policy makers because it will assist to set relevant and enforceable policies. Shareholders will get relevant information regarding wealth assessment as well as capacity and integrity of management. It will reflect the investors' confidence in the financial reporting process. Students will use the work to guide them for further studies and even do their home works.

Plan of the Study

In addition to section one which is the introduction, the study will be in five sections. Section two contains review of concepts of dependent and independent variable, empirical review and theoretical review. Section three contains research methods, sample size and sampling technique, how the research data is extracted and analysed. Section four of the study is the presentation and analyses of the data. Section five contains summary conclusions and recommendations.

2. Literature Review

Concept of Real Earnings Management (REM)

Earnings manipulation takes place when executives exercise discretion in financial reporting and in shaping transactions to modify financial statements, either to deceive certain stakeholders about the actual economic performance of the firm or to impact contractual results based on reported accounting figures (Healy & Wahlen, 1999). According to Schipper (1989) REM takes place resulting from top management efforts to modify the arrangement or timing of activities, financial transfers, acquisitions or disposals deliberately to manipulate the preparation and presentation of the accounting figures in companies annual financial statements. The study of Roychowdhury (2006); Gunny (2005) stressed on overproduction and discretionary expenses as the two operational measures of REM. Sun, Liu and Lan (2014) described REM as the managerial manipulations in activities of company's operations which directly affects the cash flow of the company. Ana and Younghwan (2022) posited that there is consistently a disagreement

of interest between shareholders and management due to the dis-agreement of incentives and differing interests.

Ibrahim and Abubakar (2020) defined REM as management actions taken by moving from day-day business activities in order to attain certain threshold in earnings. According to Roychowdhury (2006) chief executives of companies adopt different tools of REM. Srivastava (2019) posited that rem is the actions of management which deviates from the business practices that are conducted in normal business operations with the main aim of achieving targeted profit which is conducted mainly in three (3) methods: the first is the operating cash flow manipulations, the second is overproduction, and the third is reduced discretionary expenses. Ayisi, et al. (2021) defined REM as the process whereby the management of company changes its operating activities such in such a way that profits in the current period will increase. They contended that real activity manipulations takes place in several ways; in order to increase profits in the current year through altering research and development, producing more than required to reduce expenses of sales or reducing some costs that are desirable.

Audit Committee

A sub-committee established by the board of directors which comprise of non-executive directors entirely is known as Audit committee. The SOX Act (2002) describes the audit committee as an established sub-committee of the board purposely for an oversight function in the financial reporting process of a company. The Nigerian code of corporate governance (2018) requires the composition of the audit committee to have 3 non-executive directors as the minimum number of members of the committee which one member must be a financial expertise, there should be a minimum of two meetings to be held by the committee every year. The role to be played by the committee is to review, to assess and oversight of the remaining accounting system and internal control functions of the company. The delegation of the internal control and accounting system by the board of directors to the audit committee is to assist and ensure that the main profit objective of the company and continuity is achieved by management. Setin and Murwaningsari (2018) added that audit committee has the task of verifying that the procedures for collecting and monitoring internal information is guaranteed, ensure consistent accounting policies are adopted in the process of financial reporting for consolidation of group financial statements of entities and corporate social responsibility and relevance.

Empirical Review

Widya and Widi (2019) made an attempt to examine the effect of gender diversity EM of listed manufacturing firms in Indonesia for 5 years period (2013-2017). They used multiple regression technique to analyse the extracted data and findings revealed that gender of AC members play a significant role in reducing the level of EM practice in manufacturing firms in Indonesia. The study was based on only gender diversity ignoring other important components of corporate governance which in this study have introduced other additional variables and again the period of the study is 2017 but in this study the study period is extended to 2020 making it current.

Mamant and Amarjeet (2016) examined the role of AC characteristics on EM in Indian firms for three years (2013-2015) by utilising data from 130 sample companies. The study adopted the multiple regression techniques and findings revealed that only AC size, multiple directorship and frequency of meetings of AC have played significant role in restraining EM. This study has captured a wider study period than the study under review which will give a better insight on the subsisting variables. The study was conducted in India paving environmental gap to be filled and undertaken in Nigerian context.

Omar (2017) examined the relationship between AC characteristics and EM in Bahrain for a study period of 3years from 2012 to 2014, a 95 year firm observations was arrived from the data that was extracted from a sample of 31 companies out of a population of 42 listed companies in Bahrain Stock exchange. Multivarite technique was adopted to analyse the data and results revealed that AC size and AC financial expertise was negatively correlated with EM while independence of AC and meetings held by the AC was negatively correlated with EM. The study adopted accruals as EM proxy however in this study, real activities manipulations is proxy for EM.

Alhassan, Gololo and Islam (2019) examined the relationship between AC and EM from a sample of 10 companies in listed manufacturing firms in Nigeria for ten year period spanning 2010-2019. Random effect model was employed in analysing the secondary data and the results revealed that share ownership of AC and financial expertise of AC has significant negative relationship with EM while AC tenure had an insignificant negative relationship with EM. However, the study employed only three variables for AC but in this study more variables will be adopted, and again the REM will be adopted for EM. Again, in this study the whole listed non-financial firms are considered which will give a wider understanding than only one sector considered in the study under review.

Agency Theory

This study used the agency to describe the existing relationship between audit committee and real earnings management of listed conglomerate firms in Nigeria. The concept of agency theory was introduced by Jensen and Mackling (1976). They applied the concept of agency cost to explain issues associated with the separation of ownership and control in large corporations (entity concept of Accounting). The agency theory is the core of the principal agent relationship which is between the shareholders and the managers acting as agents whose personal interest does not always adhere with the company and the shareholder interest (Tyokoso et al, 2015). In an agency relationship the shareholders are the principal while management is the agent but as a result of the entity concept that restricts shareholders to participate in the day to day running of the company, shareholders must have a party who will represent them in taking decisions. Therefore, an appropriately constituted audit committee is established by the board of directors to act on behalf of the shareholders and an appropriately performing function of the audit committee will help to resolve agency problem arising between top management and shareholders of a company who are owners (providers of capital) of the company. And in return the financial performance and financial position of the company will effectively be enhanced thereby achieving the ultimate objective of the company expected by stakeholders.

Methodology

This study adopts the ex-post factor research design because of the relationship that exists between the dependent variable and independent variables of the study. The population of the study consist of all the non-financial firms listed in NSE as at 31st-Dec-2020. Because of available of data and nature of the components of the Srivastava (2019) model, only 76 companies will consist of the sample in the study to form 760 firm year observations. Data is extracted from published individual company financial statements. The multiple linear regression technique is employed to analyse the secondary data.

Model Specification

The residuals of Srivastava (2019) are used to measure earnings management and it is specified as follows:

$$PC_{it} = \alpha_1 + \alpha_2 \times 1/T A_{it-1} + \alpha_3 \times SL_{it}/TA_{it-1} + \alpha_4 \times \Delta SL_{it}/TA_{it-1} + \alpha_5 \times \Delta SL_{it-1}/TA_{it-1} + \alpha_6 \times \text{LogMV}_{it} + \alpha_7 \times \text{LogROA}_{it} + \alpha_8 \times M/B_{it} + \alpha_9 \times SL_{it+1}/TA_{it-1} + \alpha_{10} \times \text{ProductionCost}_{it-1} + \mu_t$$

Where:

PC = Production Cost (COGS + change in inventory)

$\alpha^*(1/TA_{it-1})$ = scaled intercept of previous year

- TA_{it-1} = total assets of previous year
- $\alpha_1 - \alpha_{10}$ = parameters for estimating coefficient
- SL = sales at present year
- ΔSL = change in sales
- MV = Market Value
- ROA = Return on Assets
- M/B = Market to book value
- μ = residuals = Real activities management (RAM)
- i = industry
- t = time

The mathematical models of the study are presented below:

$$REM_{it} = a_0 + a_1 CMTEIND_{it} + a_2 CMTSIZ_{it} + a_3 CMTDIV_{it} + a_4 CMTMEE_{it} + a_5 FRMSIZ_{it} + \mu_i \dots \dots \dots \text{model (1)}$$

Where:

- REM = Real Earnings Management
- CMTE = Audit committee
- IND = Independence
- MET = Meetings
- SIZ = Size
- DIV = Diversity
- FRMSIZ = Firm Size (control Variable)
- a₀ = Intercept
- a₁+a₅ = Co- efficient of independent variables μ = Term Error

Table 1

s/n	Variable	Measurement
1	Real Earnings management	Residuals of (Srivastava, 2019) model.
2	Audit committee independence	We code sample companies 1 if their audit committees are entirely composed of independent members in each year during the sample period and 0 otherwise.
3	audit committee meetings	We code sample companies 1 if the audit committee met at least four times in each year during the sample period and 0 otherwise.

4	Audit committee size	We code a sample company 1 if they have above three members on their audit committee in each year during the sample period and 0 otherwise.
5	Audit committee financial expertise	We code sample company 1 if there is a financial expertise as a member in the audit committee and 0 if otherwise.

Source: Authors' 2023

Presentation and Analysis of Data

In this section of the study the descriptive statistics, correlation matrix and the summary of the regression result is presented, interpreted, discussed and hypotheses of the study were tested accordingly.

Table 2: Categorisation of companies by each sector

S/N	Type	Code	Number of companies	Percentage %	No. of observations
1	Agriculture	1	5	6.6	50
2	Conglomerates	2	6	7.9	60
3	Healthcare	3	9	11.8	90q
4	Consumer goods	4	20	26.3	200
5	Industrial goods	5	13	17.1	130q
6	Natural resources	6	4	5.3	40
7	Oil and gas	7	12	15.8	120
8	Services	8	7	9.2	70
Total sample size			76	100	760

Source: Researchers computation, 2023

Table 3: descriptive statistics

Variables	Mean	Std.Dev	Min	Max
REM	5.960254	6.159268	.0003388	71.18352
CMTIND	47.78601	13.66158	0.000	100.00
CMTSIZ	5.486129	.9980831	2.000	9.000
CMTDIV	19.02785	92.20069	0.000	2525.0
CMTMEE	3.891678	.85381	1.000	10.000

Source: STATA 11 output listing, 2023

The descriptive statistics is presented which shows the nature of all the variables selected in the study.

From the Table 3, real earnings management of the listed non-financial firms in Nigeria has a mean value of 5.960254, maximum value of 71.18352 and minimum value of .0003388 and a standard deviation of 6.159268 respectively. Furthermore, audit committee independence has a mean value of 47.78601, a maximum value of 100.00 and a minimum value of 0.000, and a standard deviation of 13.66158 respectively. In addition, the table 3 also shows that audit committee size has a mean value 5.486129, a maximum value of 9.000 and a minimum value of 2.000, and a standard deviation of .9980831 respectively. The table 3 also shows that audit committee diversity has a minimum and maximum value of 0.000 and 2525.0 with a standard deviation of 92.20069 and a mean value of 19.02785. Finally, audit committee meetings show a standard deviation value of .85381, a mean value of 3.891678, and a minimum and maximum value of 1.000 and 10.000 respectively.

Table 4: Correlation matrix

	REM	CMTIND	CMTSIZ	CMTDIV	CMTMEE
REM	1.0000				
CMTIND	0.0158	1.0000			
CMTSIZ	0.0284	0.0189	1.0000		
CMTDIV	0.1005	0.0102	0.0697	1.0000	
CMTMEE	-0.0039	0.0175	0.2497	0.1002	1.0000

Source: STATA 11 output listing, 2023

Table 4 shows that REM is positively correlated with CMTIND, CMTSIZ and CMTDIV only at 0.0158, 0.0284 and 0.0284. While CMTMEE is negatively correlated with REM to the tune of -0.0039. Furthermore, all the independent variables are correlated with each other and this suggests a direct relationship between the subsisting variables.

Table 5: Multi-collinearity Test

Variables	VIF	1/VIF
CMTIND	1.00	0.999408
CMTSIZ	1.07	0.935437
CMTDIV	1.01	0.987772
CMTMEE	1.07	0.930621
Mean VIF		1.04

Source: STATA 11 output listing, 2023

The mean VIF in the table 5 above shows a value of 1.04 which is not less and this implies that multi-collinearity will not pose a threat to the analysis of the study. The essence of the VIF test is to determine the existence of multi-collinearity in the data.

Table 6: Regression result

Variable	Coefficients	T-value	P-Value
CMTIND	-.0007876	-0.05	0.959
CMTSIZ	-.0298865	-0.11	0.914
CMTDIV	.0064573	10.93	0.000
CMTMEE	-.0811383	-0.34	0.736
R-square			0.0100
Chi2			140.53
F-Sig			0.0000

Source: STATA 11 output summary

The multiple co-efficient of audit committee independence from the table 6 shows a value of -.0007876 and a t-value of -0.05 with an insignificant p-value of 0.959, this implies that audit committee independence has no significant impact on real earnings management of listed non-financial firms in Nigeria. The result is contrary to the priori expectation of this study and also contrary to the agency theory which the committee is expected to act on behalf of the shareholders but the result only justifies the agency theory assumption that conflict of interest is expected to arise between providers of capital of a company and management of the entity.

From the Table 6, the co-efficient value of audit committee size shows a value of -.0298865 and a –value of -0.11 which is insignificant at a value of 0.914. This implies that audit committee size has no significant impact in reducing real earnings management in the non-financial firms listed in Nigeria. This result is also contrary to prior expectations and also contrary to the agency theory this is because the number of members in the audit committee is expected to curtail the level of real earnings management in the listed non-financial firms in Nigeria.

Furthermore, from the Table 6, audit committee diversity shows a co-efficient value of .0064573 and a p-value of 10.93 which is significant at 99% confidence level. This signifies that audit committee diversity is positively and significantly contributing to real earnings management. This implies that for every one unit increase in audit committee diversity, real earnings management of listed non-financial firms in Nigeria will increase by the co-

efficient value. The result is not surprising because it is believed by many scholars that the involvement of women in management will drastically reduce the level of real earnings management in an entity.

More so, the Table 6 showed that audit committee meetings have a value of co-efficient of -.0811383 and a t-value of -0.34 with an insignificant p-value of 0.736. This implies that audit committee meetings do not have any significant impact on real earnings management of listed non-financial firms in Nigeria.

For the fitness of the model of the study and chosen variables, R^2 showed a value of 0.0100 which implies that all the variables of the study combined explain only 1% of real earnings management while the remain percentage is explained by other factors not captured in the study. The value of the F-statistics 140.53 which is significant at 99% level of confidence suggests that the variables of the study are fit and properly selected.

5. Summary, Conclusion and Recommendations

The study set to examine the impact of audit committee on real earnings management of listed non-financial firms in Nigeria and this is because of the recent published fraud cases in Nigeria in the oil & gas industry, aviation industry and manufacturing industry. Most of the reasons of the fraud were highly hung on the lack of integrity and negligence of the audit committee who serve as the representative of the board in overseeing responsibilities. The dependent variable of the study is proxy by the revised model of Srivastava (2019) and the independent variable is the committee on audit in the listed non-financial firms in Nigeria. The study period is from 2011-2020 due to availability of data. Various studies have been reviewed for the purpose of this study but the findings were mixed and as such inconclusive and the study also adopted the agency theory to underpin the study in order to explain the relationship between real earnings management and audit committee.

In conclusion the study found out that audit committee independence has no significant impact on real earnings management of listed non-financial firms in Nigeria. The result also proved that audit committee size is not sufficient to curtail the level of earning management to the barest minimum. Audit committee meetings also did not pose any significance in mitigating real earnings management. However, only audit committee diversity was able to exert significant impact on real earnings management in the study. From the result of the study, the study fails to reject H_{01} , H_{02} and H_{04} of the study while H_{01} is rejected.

Going by the result of this study, the following recommendations are proffered:

Firstly, it is recommended that the composition of the audit committee in the listed non-financial firms in Nigeria should be increased to six with equal number of executive directors and non-executive directors as this will increase the capacity of the audit committee competency.

Again, it should be mandated by the relevant authorities that in the composition of every audit committee specifically in the listed non-financial firms in Nigeria must involve women who should form up-to 30% and above of the gender percentage as this will help in women participation in the committee. Furthermore, the minimum number of annual audit committee meetings should also be increased to six and above as the frequent meetings will help the committee to keep up-to date with the activities of the accounting and internal control system of the entity.

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